

Merchandiser Perception of Cashless Transaction A Case Study of District Meerut of Uttar Pradesh State in India

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Abstract

Digital payment is a future of cashless economy and most of Indians are using Digital payment for their transaction but after demonetization it feels like a compulsory for all but not enforceable by law of India. Suddenly the change in economy, this is not easy to covert from cash to cashless due to unavailability of infrastructure facility for this cashless platform. General people discuss some issues and benefits with each and on other side merchandisers were very embarrassing due to new way of currency transaction. The regular practises of physical transaction of money are going to be changed and all transaction will be in records is good for economy but merchandiser having different perceptions related to different aspects. In this paper an attempt is made to examine the merchandisers of Meerut (Uttar Pradesh) perception towards cashless transaction and conclusion are made based on the finding. The Research objectives are

- 1. To Investigate the Reason of conversion from cash to Cashless transactions*
- 2. To analyse the challenges and prospects for Cashless transactions in district Meerut of Uttar Pradesh in India.*

Keywords: *Merchandiser, cashless transaction, perception, demonetized.*

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Introduction

In conjunction with demonetization, the government has announced waivers on convenience charges, surcharge and service charge on digital payments by government departments and organizations to promote digital and card-based payments. The announcement of demonetization of Big Rupees note denomination notes of Rs. 500 and Rs.1000 worth nearly 15.4 trillion, took place on November 8, 2016. That move to reduce corruption, black money, eliminating counterfeit currency and terrorism funding. on moving towards a cashless economy and creating an Indian Cashless society, for betterment of Indian economy and encouraged people of India, to use cashless transactions, consider mobile phone usage, as a wallet and a bank.

A merchandiser is someone who ensures that the correct amounts of products are on hand in a store or on websites. So easily we can say merchandisers are of two types

- 1. Traditional Merchandisers** – who are using old platform of transaction or say physical transaction.
- 2. Modern Merchandiser** — who are using latest platform of transaction or say cashless/digital transaction.

Traditional Merchandisers and modern merchandiser are having different thoughts on cashless transaction in District like Meerut of Uttar Pradesh in India. District Meerut in Uttar Pradesh having its own place in trade and Commerce in India.

Meerut is also having own important space in the Indian history. The district is bounded on the north by Muzaffarnagar district, on the South by Ghaziabad, Bulandsahar&Gautambudh Nagar districts and on the East by Bijnore&Jyotibaphule Nagar districts and on the West by Baghpat district. The whole district is a vast level plain. Ganga &Hindon Rivers draws the Eastern & Western boundaries of the district.

MAP OF MEERUT

Population (Meerut)

Gender	Male	Female	Total
No.	752,893	668,009	1,420,902

Source: www.census2011.co.in

Gender Ratio (Meerut)

Gender	Male	Female
No.	1000	887

Source: www.census2011.co.in

Literacy Rate (Meerut)

Gender	Male	Female	Total
Percentage	81.57%	70.36%	76.28%

Source: www.census2011.co.in

Agriculture Land Use (Meerut)

Components	Area ('000 ha)	Cropping Intensity (%)
Net sown area	198.941	152.67%
Area sown more than once	104.783	
Gross cropped area	303.724	

Source: www.allduniv.ac.in

S.No	Banks	Numbers
1	Commercial Banks	297
2	Rural Banks Products	2
3	Co-operative Banks Products	34
4	PLDB Branches	4

Source: District Stat. & Eco. Office, Meerut (2011)

S.No.	Name of Industrial Units
1	Bhalla International udyogpuram Industrial Estate , Meerut
2	Mawana Sugar Works, Mawana, Meerut
3	Dayal Fertilizer Pvt Ltd, Meerut
4	Mankind Pharma Ltd, Meerut
5	Alps Industries Ltd., Delhi Road, Meerut
6	Sai Electricals , Balwant Nagar , Meerut
7	Arihanprakashan, Meerut
8	Devpriya Papers Pvt. Ltd., Sani, Mawana Road, Meerut

Review of Literature

Al-Laham (2009) found that there was considerable interest in the development of electronic money schemes in recent years. He also said that E-money could become the future platform of currency transactions in the world. K. Sree Latha Reddy and S. Jaya Laxmi (2014) comparative study on Traditional shopping and Online shopping and found that Online shopping is most convenient and time efficient and also cost cutting exercise as one need not to step out of his / her home for doing shopping and Traditional shopping still allows ground to the consumer in terms of physically analyse and even try out the merchandise that he wants. The main point is that you would always be find the best means to whatever feasible you in both the money factor and the need or want factor. Er. Harjot Kaur and Mrs. Daljit Kaur (2015) studies a E-Commerce in India – Challenges and Prospects and he found that E-commerce is the extensive use of computer network with internet. Deepika Kumari (2016) found that Government do efforts to aware its citizen for cashless transaction by different kinds of advertisement method but after doing such efforts a large number of people are remaining to introduction of cashless transaction. Sheetal Thomas & G. Krishnamurthi (2016) examined that there is enormous potential that rural economy in India can become a cashless economy.

Shamsher Singh and Ravish Rana (2017) studies of consumer perception of digital payment mode and found that in the educated areas such as Delhi NCR and other metropolitan cities, the of acceptance of digital payment is high . The Smartphone

and internet penetration growth in such area also facilitated the adoption of digital payment. Dr. Chandravathi (2018) attempt to understand Merchant's perception towards cashless economy and he found that the people are mentally ready for adoption of modern online technology driven facilities for their day today transactions leading to use of less cash in the economy . It also appears that many people actually agree with the government on the usefulness of the cashless economy. It is agreed that the cashless system will be helpful in the fight against corruption and money laundering. One most significant contribution of the cashless economy is that it is expected to reduce the risk associated with carrying cash

Methodology

The research mainly used primary data and was collected with the help of questionnaire through survey method. These questionnaires consist of total ten questions and out of which four questions are related to profile of respondents. Questionnaire are based on Five level Likert scale. The sample size of the study is 100 respondents and population of the study consists from different type of business owners from District Meerut of state uttar Pradesh. Total population was divided into four part of Meerut as a North- East, North- West, South-East and South-west. Strata simple random sampling technique is used using random number of tables. Collected data is analysed by calculating percentage. Chi-square test is used for testing the hypothesis.

Table 1.1: Gender of the Respondent

Gender	Number of respondent	Percentages %
Male	69	69
Female	31	31
Total	100	100

Out of 100 respondents surveyed, 69 percent are males and 31 percent are female.

Table 1.2: age of the respondent

Age	Number of respondent	Percentages %
Below 30 years	27	27
Between 31 - 40 years	29	29
Between 41 - 55 years	36	36
Above 55 years	8	8
Total	100	100

Out of 100 respondents surveyed, the age of 27 percent respondent is below 30 years, 29 percent respondents age is between 31-40 years, 36 percent respondents age is between 41-55 years, 8 percent respondents age is above 55 years.

Table 1.3: monthly Income of the respondent

Income (Rs)	Number of respondent	Percentage %
Below 15000	18	18
Between 15001 -50000	35	35
Between 50001- 100000	26	26
Above 100000	21	21
Total	100	100

Out of 100 respondents surveyed, the income of 18 percent respondent is below Rs 15000, 35 percent respondents income is between Rs 15001-50000, 26 percent respondents income is between Rs 50001-100000, 21 percent respondents income is above 100000.

Table 1.4: Education of the respondent

Education	Number of respondent	Percentage
Below High School	19	19
Between HS to Intermediate	21	21
Between Intermediate to Graduation	46	46
Between Graduation to PG	14	14
Total	100	100

Out of 100 respondents surveyed, the Education of 19 percent respondent is below High School, 21 percent respondents education is between High School to Intermediate, 46 percent respondents education is between intermediate to Graduation, 14 percent respondents education is between Graduations to PG.

Table 2:1 Response on “to reduce Corruption is the reason for cashless Payment in Meerut”

S.N	Opinion	Number of Respondent	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	23	23
2	Agree	38	38
3	Neutral	15	15
4	Disagree	14	14
5	Strongly Disagree	10	10
	TOTAL	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table indicates the response of merchandiser about that to reduce the Corruption is the reason for cashless payment in Meerut.

It is concluded that the Majority of the Merchandisers (61%) felt that Corruption is the reason for cashless payment in Meerut.

χ^2 test

H0: Corruption in transaction has no influence on Merchandiser for cashless Transaction in Meerut for merchandiser.

H1: Corruption in transaction has an influence on Merchandiser for cashless Transaction in Meerut for merchandiser.

Observed Frequency (O _i)	Expected Frequency(E _i)	(O _i – E _i)	(O _i – E _i) ²	(O _i – E _i) ² /E _i
23	20	3	9	0.45
38	20	18	324	16.2
15	20	-5	25	1.25
14	20	-6	36	1.8
10	20	-10	100	5
Total χ^2				24.7

Calculated value of $\chi^2= 24.7$. The Critical value of χ^2 at 4 Degree of Freedom at 5% level of Significance is 9.488. Calculated value is Greater than Critical Value i.e., $24.7 > 9.488$, Hence, Ho is Rejected.

Table 2.2 Response on “safety issue during cash mobilisation is the main concern for cashless Payment in Meerut”

S.N	Opinion	Number of Respondent	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	36	36
2	Agree	29	29
3	Neutral	12	12
4	Disagree	13	13
5	Strongly Disagree	10	10
	TOTAL	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table indicates the response of merchandiser about that safety issue during cash mobilisation is the main concern for cashless payment in Meerut. It is concluded that the Majority of the Merchandisers (51%) felt that safety issue during cash mobilisation is the main concern for cashless payment in Meerut. **test**
H0:Safety issue during cash mobilisation has no influence on Merchandiser for cashless Payment in Meerut.

H1: safety issue during cash mobilisation has influence on Merchandiser for cashless Payment in Meerut.

Observed Frequency (O _i)	Expected Frequency(E _i)	(O _i – E _i)	(O _i – E _i) ²	(O _i – E _i) ² /E _i
36	20	16	256	12.8
29	20	9	81	4.05
12	20	-8	64	3.2
13	20	-7	49	2.45
10	20	-10	100	5
Total χ^2				27.5

Calculated value of $\chi^2= 27.5$ The Critical value of χ^2 at 4 Degree of Freedom at 5% level of Significance is 9.488. Calculated value is Greater than Critical Value i.e., $27.5 > 9.488$, Hence, H_0 is Rejected.

Table 2.3 Response on “Internet speed in India is a big obstacle for cashless Transaction ”

S.N	Opinion	Number of Respondent	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	43	43
2	Agree	38	38
3	Neutral	5	5
4	Disagree	12	12
5	Strongly Disagree	2	2
	TOTAL	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table indicates the response of merchandiser about that Internet speed in India is a big obstacle for cashless Transaction.

It is concluded that the Majority of the Merchandisers (81%) felt that Internet speed in India is a big obstacle for cashless Transaction² **test**

H₀:Internet speed in India has no influence on Merchandiser for cashless Payment in Meerut.

H₁: Internet speed in India has influence on Merchandiser for cashless Payment in Meerut.

Payment in Meerut.

Observed Frequency (O _i)	Expected Frequency(E _i)	(O _i – E _i)	(O _i – E _i) ²	(O _i – E _i) ² /E _i
43	20	23	529	26.45
38	20	18	324	16.2
5	20	-15	225	11.25
12	20	-8	64	3.2
2	20	-18	324	16.2
Total χ^2				73.3

Calculated value of $\chi^2= 73.3$. The Critical value of χ^2 at 4 Degree of Freedom at 5% level of Significance is 9.488. Calculated value is Greater than Critical Value

Table 2.4 Response on “Redressal system for fail transactions is Challenge for Cashless Transaction”.

S.N	Opinion	Number of Respondent	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	33	33
2	Agree	31	31
3	Neutral	12	12
4	Disagree	13	13
5	Strongly Disagree	11	11
	TOTAL	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table indicates the response of merchandiser about that Redressal system for fail transactions is Challenge for Cashless Transaction.

It is concluded that the Majority of the Merchandisers (64%) felt that Redressal system for fail transactions is Challenge for Cashless Transaction.

Observed Frequency (O _i)	Expected Frequency (E _i)	(O _i - E _i)	(O _i - E _i) ²	(O _i - E _i) ² /E _i
33	20	13	169	8.45
31	20	11	121	6.05
12	20	-8	64	3.2
13	20	-7	49	2.45
11	20	-9	81	4.05
Total χ^2				24.2

χ^2 test

H₀: Redressal system for fail transactions has no influence on Merchandiser for cashless Payment in Meerut.

H₁: Redressal system for fail transactions has influence on Merchandiser for cashless Payment in Meerut.

Observed Frequency (O _i)	Expected Frequency (E _i)	(O _i - E _i)	(O _i - E _i) ²	(O _i - E _i) ² /E _i
33	20	13	169	8.45
31	20	11	121	6.05
12	20	-8	64	3.2
13	20	-7	49	2.45
11	20	-9	81	4.05
Total χ^2				24.2

Calculated value of $\chi^2 = 24.2$. The Critical value of χ^2 at 4 Degree of Freedom at 5% level of Significance is 9.488. Calculated value is Greater than Critical Value i.e., $24.2 > 9.488$, Hence, H₀ is rejected.

Table 2.5: Response on maximum number of Customer acceptance for Cashless Transaction as compare to cash Transaction.

S.N	Opinion	Number of Respondent	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	16	16
2	Agree	14	14
3	Neutral	18	18
4	Disagree	28	28
5	Strongly Disagree	24	24
	TOTAL	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table indicates the response of merchandiser about the customers that maximum numbers of Customer accept Cashless Transaction as compare to cash Transaction. It is concluded that the Majority of the Merchandisers (52%) not felt that maximum number of Customer accept Cashless Transaction as compare to cash Transaction

χ^2 Test

:Customer accepts Cashless Transaction as compare to cash Transaction has no influence on Merchandiser for cashless transaction in Meerut.

H1: Customer accepts Cashless Transaction as compare to cash Transaction has influence on Merchandiser for cashless transaction in Meerut.

Observed Frequency (O _i)	Expected Frequency (E _i)	(O _i - E _i)	(O _i - E _i) ²	(O _i - E _i) ² / E _i
16	20	-4	16	0.8
14	20	-6	36	1.8
18	20	-2	4	0.2
28	20	8	64	3.2
24	20	4	16	0.8
Total χ^2				6.8

Calculated value of $\chi^2 = 6.8$. The Critical value of χ^2 at 4 Degree of Freedom at 5% level of Significance is 9.488. Calculated value is less than Critical Value i.e., $6.8 < 9.488$, Hence, H₀ is accepted.

Table 2.6 Response on Cashless Transaction makes merchandiser stronger against the E-Commerce websites Business to get order and payment solution across the country.

S.N	Opinion	Number of Respondent	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	12	12
2	Agree	10	10
3	Neutral	5	5
4	Disagree	41	41
5	Strongly Disagree	32	32
	TOTAL	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table indicates the response of merchandiser about that Cashless Transaction makes merchandiser stronger against the E-Commerce websites Business to get order and payment solution across the country.

It is concluded that the Majority of the Merchandisers (73%) not felt that Cashless Transaction makes merchandiser stronger against the E-Commerce websites Business to get order and payment solution across the country

χ^2 test

H₀: Cashless Transaction makes merchandiser stronger against the E-Commerce websites Business to get order and payment solution across the country has no influence on Merchandiser for cashless transaction in Meerut
H₁: Cashless Transaction makes merchandiser stronger against the E-Commerce websites Business to get order and payment solution across the country has influence on Merchandiser for cashless transaction in Meerut.

Observed Frequency (O _i)	Expected Frequency (E _i)	(O _i – E _i)	(O _i – E _i) ²	(O _i – E _i) ² /E _i
12	20	-8	64	3.2
10	20	-10	100	5
5	20	-15	225	11.2
41	20	21	441	22.05
32	20	12	144	7.2
Total χ^2				48.65

Calculated value of $\chi^2=48.65$ The Critical value of χ^2 at 4 Degree of Freedom at 5% level of Significance is 9.488. Calculated value is Greater than Critical Value i.e., $48.65 > 9.488$, Hence, H₀ is rejected

Conclusion:

As the Response of the merchandiser in the district Meerut of Uttar Pradesh that merchandiser are negative point of view towards cashless Commerce due to safety issue during cash mobilisation, internet speed in India and Redressal system for fail transactions but on the point of Corruption and Competition against E-Commerce Websites merchandiser are having positive thinking towards cashless commerce and also think maximum customer uses cash as compare to cashless. Finally the Research conclude that merchandiser in District Meerut of State Uttar Pradesh in India will have positive perception towards cashless transaction perception if Government and banking system provide good infrastructure for cashless Transaction.

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